

THE STUDY OF LEXICAL NORMS AND THEIR SPECIFIC FEATURES

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Annotation. This article talks about the study of language levels in world linguistics, as well as the need to create a lexical basis of levels in the modern Uzbek literary language.

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Language is the main means of preserving and enriching our spiritual heritage. Preservation of languages means preservation of national spirituality. After all, original spirituality exists only in national form. In our country, attention to language has risen to the level of one of the priority areas of attention to spirituality. Therefore, it has become an urgent task to preserve and enrich our native language, increase the effectiveness of its practical use, and to achieve the widespread use of the Uzbek language in the modern information and communication system. Because the promotion of our mother tongue to the world is one of the main ways to improve and raise national spirituality.

Modern information technologies have opened the door to a wide range of possibilities for using the functional capabilities of the language. Computer translation, editing, analysis, electronic dictionaries and thesaurus are proof of our opinion. Creating a culture of creating modern electronic dictionaries and using them is especially important in expanding language opportunities. In our republic, great attention is being paid to the effective use of information technologies in every field, and to projects based on software. In this regard, several decisions, decrees and orders of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been adopted. In particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2002 "On further development of computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies", the Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 11, 2003 "On information law, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 1, 2012 No. PQ-1730 "On measures to introduce and develop modern information and communication technologies" and the like.

One of the most important issues facing our applied linguistics today is to create the lexical, morphological and syntactic basis of the first, second and third levels of the Uzbek language. Relying on world experience, it is necessary to create a lexical basis of the levels of the Uzbek language, taking into account the nature of the Uzbek language. The following are important in the interlinguistic gradation of the language:

- To study the scope of the lexical level of the language, that is, to get acquainted with the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language;
- Forming the skill of effective use of frequency dictionaries in lexical grading;
- Familiarization with methods of language teaching and assessment;
- Development of special experimental methods for pupils, students and language learners in determining the lexical coverage important for the first level;
- Comparison and harmonization of European standard and DTS requirements in language teaching and assessment;
- Grading the lexical level and thereby recommending the creation of Uzbek language profiles, etc.

The theory and grammatical laws of modern Uzbek linguistics began to be systematized in the 20th century according to the system nature of the language. At a time when the time has come to approach the systematic practice based on these theories in linguistics, it is time to upgrade the Uzbek literary language. Based on the theory and practice of world linguistics, based on CEFR and IELTS rules and skills, a new grading pattern of our native language will be created. The leveling of the language was carried out on the scale of languages of international status and world languages, and is a theoretical and practical innovation for the Uzbek literary language.

The state language of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek language, was also formed as a literary language as a result of historical development, and currently has more than fifty million users around the world. With the increase in the number of Uzbek language users, the development of perfect grammar of the Uzbek language and the establishment of easy and clear standards for teaching it will not only help foreigners learn the language, but also serve to increase the literacy of the Uzbek people. The uniqueness of international languages is due to the fact that their grammar is graded as a common teaching and learning model for everyone based on certain norms and rules. In all languages of the world, universal typological phenomena are also valid for the methods of their study, that is, the theory and practical methodology of languages mutually feed each

other. Based on this, the grading of the Uzbek literary language makes a radical turn in linguistics as a phenomenon based on modernity and accuracy. For this, first of all, it is necessary to get acquainted with the linguistically graded languages, their laws, the principles of grading, and to determine the general and differential aspects of the graded languages. In this regard, we base ourselves on the ranking of the English language, which is the most widespread in our country and the number of people interested in other languages.

Lexical norms mean the correct choice and appropriate use of words in the common language during speech. Ambiguity, a large number of choices within lexical units in the form of synonyms and variants also caused the formation of its own standards. Reflecting on the normative features of dialectism, neologism and occasionalism, pleonism and other lexical units in our language expands our perception of the lexical norm.

Setting standards within dialectics and literary language standards is considered one of the responsible issues in our language. Because the literary language selects words common to most of them from the dialect lexicon and includes them in its lexicon (for example, cow-cow-cow; baby-boob, egg-testicle-egg, ant-ant -karinja-kumuruska, etc.).

There are exact equivalents in Uzbek and considered as barbarism: nu, tak, vot, sovsem, voobshchye, tolko, tolko tak, yestestvenno, obyazatelno, konechno, uje, pochti, tak chto, znachit, kak raz, neujeli, tem boleye, document The use of words and phrases such as , oformit, organizovat, prinimat, razresheniye olma, put podpis, bo, akun, soni is also not a positive phenomenon. Here too, the norm is violated.

In connection with the creation of the Law "On the State Language", an opportunity was created to carry out reforms in the field of terminology in various fields of science, to "Uzbekize" them.

Such a situation has arisen that the enthusiasm for "nationalization" of terms has increased. Recommendations have also increased tremendously. In addition to funny ideas, difficult to digest proposals were also thrown into the middle. Here are some examples to confirm this statement: mathematics-mathematics, faculty-college, artist-painter, newspaper-customer, auditorium-classroom, room, study room, circus-auditorium, circle-pargar, cellophane-wall paper. , safe-envelope, attestation-examination, airplane-airplane, ready, airport-training ground, surname-genealogy, club-invitation room, title list-list, etc. But these views are remarkable in the sense that they contain the idea of cleaning the language as much as possible from foreign elements.

Author, architect, humanism, доклад, ideology, inspector, intelligent, control, command, komanirovochnaya, lecture, minister, oblast, stop, planet, problem, district, report, editor, revolution, spravka, student, secretary, used in our language, theme, territory, tradition, form, etc which are replaced by author, architect, humanitarian, lecture, ideology, supervisor, intellectual, control, journey, travelogue, lecture, minister, region, station, planet, problem, district, notification / notification, editor, revolution, information / reference, student, secretary / secretary, subject, area, tradition, form, etc., were easily acquired. Because they were more or less used as doublets in our language before. It follows that the acceptance and normalization of the newly recommended words depends on whether they have been used in the language before or not.

Here, let's analyze an example. In the process of searching for alternatives to many terms, instead of the word "rayon", the words "nohiya", "depara" and "tuman" began to be used. Later, although it does not correspond to the original meaning of the word, the word district became normal. However, it should be noted that this word has only one meaning - the term of an administrative region that is a part of a region and has a certain border. However, the dictionary also shows the possibility of the word district meaning a place in general: prigorodnyy rayon - suburban district, promyshlennyy rayon - industrial district, zavodskoy rayon - factory district, rayon voyennyx deystviy - war effort district, rayon dye - a battlefield, oboronitelny rayon - such as a defensive circle. How do we standardize these compounds? Since it is currently being formed in our minds as an administrative region, can it be normalized in the form of a suburban district, a district of factories, a district of war operations? In addition, there are the words rayonirovaniye, rayonirovanny - regionalization, regionalized, which are derived from the root of this word. For example, regionalization of the seeds of certain crop varieties, that is, the seeds of varieties that are most adapted to the conditions of a place.

How do we normalize this? Is it fogging the seed or placing the seed, adapting the seed to the places? In any case, the solution to the problem will be solved over time. Lexemes are divided into 2 groups in terms of their scope of use: layer with unlimited scope of use and layer with limited scope of use. Separation into such groups is mainly characteristic of lexemes in the categories of nouns, adjectives, adverbs and verbs. There are no restricted words in the categories of number and pronouns, as well as conjunctions, prepositions, and exclamations.

Lexemes with unlimited scope of use are words that are common to all Uzbek speakers, are understandable to everyone and are used equally in everyone's speech: hand, eyebrow, eye, tree, fruit (nouns); white, black, big, small, good, bad (adjectives); fast, little, many, deliberately, four (adjectives); walk, read, write (verbs) and others. Such lexemes are also called universal lexical units.

Lexemes with a limited scope of use are words characteristic of dialect, profession - craft lexeme, and jargon - slang. Vulgarisms used in live conversation are also limited lexical units. "Most of the lexemes whose usage is not limited are common Turkic and Uzbek words. However, at the same time, there are many differences among them.

For example:

Tajik: meat, bread, pain, grandfather, friend.

Arabic: generation, with, person, class, nation.

Lexemes borrowed from European languages can be both native and borrowed" [1].

Commonly used words in the Uzbek language. Such words are widely used in everyday life, understandable for many people, and are characterized by their stylistic neutrality. The widely used words of the Uzbek language have not been studied enough. "In some studies, this group of words was interpreted under the name of "lexicon without limitation in scope" [2].

In E. Begmatov's book "Lexical Layers of the Modern Uzbek Literary Language", the widely used words are divided into twenty-six different groups, each of which is explained with examples. Here are some of them:

-names of things and phenomena related to natural existence: sun, moon, water, air, sky, star, river, mountain;

- the names of the concepts representing various elements of nature: wind, storm, flood, lightning, lightning, flood, fog, earthquake;

- words expressing movement and state, as well as human labor activity: walking, standing, hitting, running, running;

Words related to the mental state of a person: to be happy, to be happy, to feel sorry, to cry;

Names of people and animals: man, woman, boy, girl; horse, bird, dog, like;

Names of human and animal parts and organs: head, foot, hand, finger, liver, lung, heart;

Relative - words related to clan: father, mother, son, daughter, sister, child, uncle, grandfather, aunt, uncle, etc.;

Words that express the relationship between people, distant - closeness: dear, kind, caring, passionate, friend, etc.

It turns out that standardization in language is a multifaceted process, words in common use are termed within the framework of a certain profession or jargon, deviate from their main standardized status, or vice versa - profession - the meaning of terms covered by private standards of craft or jargon can become public property. After all, this is one of the dimensions of language development.

But the issue of norms that we are studying is not new for our social life. Language and society exist, and this issue is also in the middle. However, each period causes its own problems of language use in connection with its development.

As the degree to which the Uzbek literary language is standardized and to what extent it is followed is one of the factors that determine the level of development of the national Uzbek culture, dealing with this problem remains an urgent task that intellectuals must solve in the future.

Today, out of more than seven thousand languages in the world, about two hundred are used as official state languages. However, the "aliveness" of a language is not measured by giving a national language the status of an official language. Increasing the prestige and status of each language in the world is related to the increase in the number of speakers of this language and the expansion of the scope of consumption. This is one of the factors determining the social viability of the language. The "aliveness" of the language, in turn, ensures the ethnic stability of that nation. Therefore, creating the lexical basis of the levels of the Uzbek language should be one of the most important tasks facing our linguistics today.

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